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Supplementary Material for **Chirped apodized fiber Bragg gratings inverse design via deep learning**

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Supplement Note 1. Electromagnetic theory

In this model, the coupled mode theory is used for coupled structures, and the Transfer Matrix Method (TMM) is used to solve coupled mode equations. The Bragg condition will efficiently reflect the light in a Fiber Bragg Grating (FBG) as follows [1]:

$$\lambda_B = 2n_{\text{eff}} \Lambda \quad (\text{S1})$$

Where the Bragg wavelength is represented by λ_B . n_{eff} denotes the effective refractive index, whereas Λ stands for the grating period.

The refractive index distribution, expressed in Figs. 1 and 2 (in the [main manuscript](#)) can be represented by a function of $n(z)$ as follows [2]:

$$n(z) = n_0 + \Delta n_{\text{dc}}(z) + A(z) \Delta n_{\text{ac}}(z) \cos((2\pi / \Lambda)z + \theta(z)) \quad (\text{S2})$$

The average refractive index change of the fiber core is denoted by n_0 . The apodization function is represented by $A(z)$. Δn_{ac} denotes the maximum index variation. The average change in refractive index is represented by Δn_{dc} . The period chirp is denoted by θ . The reflectivity of a grating can be calculated using the coupled mode theory as follows [3, 4]:

$$R(L, \lambda) = \frac{\kappa^2 \sinh^2(sL)}{\Delta\beta^2 \sinh^2(sL) + s^2 \cosh^2(sL)} \quad (\text{S3})$$

$R(L, \lambda)$ denotes the reflectivity, and L represents the grating length. The coupling constant is denoted by κ , while $\Delta\beta$ refers to the detuning wave vector and s equal to $(\kappa^2 - \Delta\beta^2)^{1/2}$. The grating period in a chirped FBG changes along its length. The chirp coefficient is used as follows to vary the period:

$$\text{period} - \frac{\alpha}{2} < \Lambda(z) < \text{period} + \frac{\alpha}{2} \quad (\text{S4})$$

Where α is the chirp coefficient, z varies between 0 and L . In this work, the following apodization functions are used to design and simulate an FBG as follows [4]:

1- Uniform

$$A(z) = 1 \quad -\frac{L}{2} \leq z \leq \frac{L}{2} \quad (\text{S5})$$

2- Cosine

$$A(z) = \cos\left(\frac{\pi z}{L}\right) \quad -\frac{L}{2} \leq z \leq \frac{L}{2} \quad (\text{S6})$$

3- Raised-Cosine

$$A(z) = \cos^2\left(\frac{\pi z}{L}\right) \quad -\frac{L}{2} \leq z \leq \frac{L}{2} \quad (\text{S7})$$

4- Tanh

$$A(z) = \frac{\tanh\left[\eta\left(1 - 2\left(\frac{z}{L}\right)\right)\right]}{\tanh(\eta)} \quad -\frac{L}{2} \leq z \leq \frac{L}{2} \quad (\text{S8})$$

The parameter η can be utilized to adjust the sharpness of the apodization profile.

Supplement Note 2: FDTD simulation of FBG

Table S1 presents the parameters utilized for simulation, which were selected based on the specified model and practical considerations involved in designing an FBG. Our study of the proposed configurations' linear and nonlinear optical properties was conducted using the Finite-Difference Time-Domain (FDTD) numerical method. We carefully chose mesh dimensions of

0.4 nm to ensure that the method accurately represented the system's visual response and improved spatial resolution. We employed a Perfectly Matched Layer (PML) as an absorptive boundary condition to minimize reflections at the simulation domain's borders. The PML has proven to be highly effective in absorbing outgoing waves and significantly reducing reflections, thereby increasing the accuracy of our findings.

Table S1. The Parameters Used in the Simulation

Parameter	Quantity
Free space wavelength, (nm)	1550
Period, (μm)	0.5
Modulation depth	0.0003
Cladding index	1.45
Fiber diameter, (μm)	5.25

This in-depth analysis gave us valuable knowledge about the unique characteristics and performance of the FBG in different situations.

Supplement Note 3: DNN formulation

We can now explore the mathematical framework underlying the forward and inverse models, having comprehensively comprehended the FBG structure depicted in Fig. 2 (in the [main manuscript](#)).

These models are crucial in structuring the problem for the Deep Neural Network (DNN), creating a nexus between the input variables and the transmission spectra. A forward model can be established by leveraging the geometric design parameters, denoted as x_i , associated with the FBG. This model enables the computation of the transmission spectrum. To ascertain the transmission spectra, y_j , the mapping function $\mathbf{M}$, and pertinent input variables can be utilized.

$$y_j = \mathbf{M}(x_1 = L, x_2 = \Lambda, x_3 = \alpha, x_4 = \Delta n_{dc}, x_5 = \Delta n_{ac}, x_6 = A(z)) \quad (\text{S9})$$

Where L is grating lengths, Λ is the grating period; α is the chirp period, Δn_{dc} is variations in the average refractive index of the fiber core, Δn_{ac} is maximum index variations, and $A(z)$ is apodization functions. For each element within the training dataset, an $A(z)$ vector denotes the inclusion or exclusion of each apodization function, such as [Uniform, Cosine, Raised-Cosine, Tanh], where a 0 value represents the absence of apodization, and a 1 indicates its application. To establish the optimal estimator, we can define an objective function to determine the best estimator for the forward model as follows:

$$\min_{i=1,2,\dots,6} \left\{ \left\| \hat{\mathbf{M}}(x_i) - \mathbf{g} \right\| \right\} \quad (\text{S10})$$

Within the equation above, the predicted function is symbolized by $\hat{\mathbf{M}}$ and undergoes comparison with the ground truth, denoted as $\mathbf{g}$, which signifies the actual observed values. The paramount challenge within Deep Learning (DL) entails the identification of the most optimal estimator for $\hat{\mathbf{M}}$ contingent on the corpus of training data at hand. Conversely, an inverse problem seeks to reconstruct the design space utilizing the extant transmission values. Our methodology distinguishes itself from conventional approaches by employing Eq. (S9) to extrapolate a design space from the transmission spectra, where y_j signifies the transmission spectra. This design space is attainable via the subsequent inverse function.

$$x_i = \mathbf{M}^{-1}(T_j) \quad (\text{S11})$$

Our research methodology stands apart by recognizing a ubiquitous challenge within our field: traditional analytical methods often prove inadequate in defining the inverse function for FBG configurations. To surmount this hurdle, our study introduces a novel perspective, proposing adopting DL strategies as an alternative solution. DL excels as a powerful tool for nonlinear approximation, and our investigation advances an improved methodology for both

forward and inverse models. This innovative approach enables a comprehensive understanding of FBG's complex behavior, marking a significant advancement in the discipline.

Supplement Note 4: Evaluation of FBG

This section will thoroughly investigate the crucial parameters that play a significant role in designing FBGs. Our objective is to carefully examine the impact of these parameters on the characteristics of FBGs. By doing so, we can use empirical knowledge in this field to evaluate the DNN's performance accurately. This analysis will provide us with a deeper understanding of the intricacies involved in the design of FBGs and how these parameters can affect the overall performance of the DNN. With this information at our disposal, we can make informed decisions and devise strategies to optimize the design of FBGs, leading to better efficiency and performance of the DNN.

A. The effects of index difference.

The index difference directly impacts reflectivity, bandwidth, and sidelobe strength, but this impact is not uniform across different lengths. We have quantified the reflectivity, bandwidth, and sidelobe strength changes as the index difference moves from 0.01 to 0.1 and then from 0.1 to 0.2. The results have been tabulated in Table S2, providing insight into the underlying dynamics. Interestingly, this table shows that when the index difference exceeds 0.1, the increase in less desirable attributes, such as sidelobe strength, outweighs the improvement in more desirable characteristics like reflectivity. As a result, index differences greater than 0.1 are not optimal. The significant increase in sidelobe strength calls for attenuation. The following section will discuss strategies for reducing sidelobe strength and optimizing FBG configurations for improved performance and utility.

Table S2. The variation in FBG characteristics when the index difference varies

Grating length (mm)	index difference	Reflectivity change (%)	Bandwidth change (nm)	Sidelobe strength change (%)
1	0.01 → 0.1	18.69	0.057	1.08
	0.1 → 0.2	2.88	0.006	0.19
3	0.01 → 0.1	48.28	0.137	8.59
	0.1 → 0.2	2.86	0.017	1.4
5	0.01 → 0.1	29.95	0.152	19.19
	0.1 → 0.2	0.58	0.017	2.71

B. The effects of apodization on reflectivity.

Figure S1 illustrates the impact of the apodization process on reflectivity. As grating length increases, reflectivity increases, reaching 100% at 15mm for uniform FBG, 24mm for Cosine apodized FBG, and 30mm for Raised-Cosine and Tanh apodized FBG. Furthermore, Fig. S1 demonstrates that the reflectivity of Raised-Cosine and Tanh apodized FBG is equivalent, with the Cosine profile boasting the highest reflectivity.

C. The effects of apodization on sidelobe strength

The primary benefit of utilizing apodization is reducing sidelobe strength. This reduction depends on the specific apodization profiles and can vary at different lengths. Figure S2 depicts the correlation between apodized FBG sidelobe strength and grating length, revealing nonlinear changes as the length increases. From the illustration, it is evident that the Raised-Cosine profile offers the lowest sidelobe strength.

D. The effects of apodization on FWHM

Choosing the appropriate bandwidth is dependent on the intended use. Figure S3 illustrates that we can alter the bandwidth through apodization. This graph illustrates that apodized FBG have wider bandwidth when their grating length is less than 3 millimeters and narrower bandwidth when the grating length is greater than 3 millimeters. As shown in Fig. S3, the Raised-Cosine profile has the highest Full Width at Half Maximum (FWHM) among the simulated apodized profiles.

Fig. S1. The reflectivity versus the grating length under different apodization profiles. The curves demonstrate how the apodization profile impacts the FBG's light reflection abilities, and the choice of the profile should be based on specific application requirements. By examining the trade-offs between FBG length and apodization profile, this graph offers valuable insights into designing FBGs with desired reflectivity properties. This data is essential for creating components for fiber optic systems that require precise control over reflectivity profiles.

Fig. S2. The sidelobe strength versus the grating length under different apodization profiles. This graph shows the sidelobe strength of three different apodization techniques - Cosine, Raised-Cosine, and Tanh - plotted against the FBG length. The graph indicates that sidelobe strength is influenced by FBG length and apodization technique. The choice of apodization technique and FBG length must be made carefully to ensure that the FBG meets specific application requirements.

Fig. S3. The FWHM versus the grating length under different apodization profiles. The graph suggests that as the FBG length increases, the bandwidth (as measured by FWHM) generally narrows for these apodization profiles. The choice of apodization function impacts the FWHM and, by extension, the spectral characteristics of the FBG, which is a critical consideration in the design of optical filtering and sensing systems.

Supplement Note 5: Dataset discussion

This section will provide a detailed overview of the training dataset utilized to train the DNN under consideration. The training dataset enables the DNN to identify hidden patterns and generate accurate predictions. With access to a complete and precise training dataset, the DNN demonstrates its ability to handle varying inputs and assign appropriate weightage via the activation function of each neuron.

Let us share some specifics to give a better idea of the dataset. Fig. S4 shows the input training dataset that was implemented to train the established DNN. The dataset used in this study comprises a whopping 27000 samples computed via the FDTD method, which is widely used in computational electromagnetics to solve Maxwell's equations numerically.

We carefully curated the dataset to ensure it is complete, accurate, and precise. It underwent rigorous testing and cleaning to eliminate noise, errors, or inconsistencies. The dataset comprises a diverse range of inputs, and we trained the DNN to handle each input type with precision and accuracy.

In conclusion, the training dataset used to train the DNN was a vital component that ensured the DNN's effectiveness in identifying hidden patterns and generating accurate predictions. The dataset was carefully curated and comprised a diverse range of inputs, and the DNN was trained to handle each input type with precision and accuracy.

Fig. S4. The histograms of the data distribution. Histograms visually represent the distribution of input and output variables. The input data set used for DNN training consists of several configurational parameters of the resonator structure, including x_1 , grating lengths; x_2 , the grating period; x_3 , the chirp period; x_4 , variations in the average refractive index of the fiber core; x_5 , maximum index variations. A histogram displays the dispersion and occurrence rates of these input factors. The uniformity across the features suggests that the input data for the NN is well-balanced, which is essential for practical model training.

Supplement Note 6: Optimizing hyperparameters of DNN

This segment delves into refining the predictive precision of DNNs by fine-tuning hyperparameters with Mean Squared Error (MSE). A uniform learning rate of 0.1 was preserved across all predictive models to guarantee optimal performance. Figure S5 illustrates a graph depicting the MSE results for a DNN that underwent 1000 training epochs, featuring 160 neurons in its central layer. The graph's independent variable is the number of hidden layers. The findings indicate that a traditional NN, equipped with a single hidden layer, does not suffice for adept prediction due to its simplicity, which is inadequate for capturing the complex interrelations within the dataset.

This research underscores the inadequacy of simpler NN architectures in addressing intricate, nonlinear problems. Conversely, more profound DNNs, akin to the one scrutinized in this study, exhibit enhanced capability in discerning and assimilating complex attributes, pivotal for tasks of substantial complexity. Notably, an augmentation in iteration numbers correlates with diminished MSE values. Additionally, as the count of hidden layers escalates, MSE values substantially decrease, reaching a plateau at 13 layers. Thus, a DNN configuration with 11 hidden layers emerged as the optimal hyperparameter setup, striking a harmonious balance between minimizing MSE outcomes and curtailing computational exigencies.

This study aimed to augment the operational efficacy of DNNs through judicious hyperparameter selection. The approach commenced by establishing a correlation between the number of hidden layers (N_L) and the neuron tally (N_n) in the central layer, as dictated by the formula $N_n=2^{(N_L-1)/2}$. Subsequently, leveraging the Fibonacci sequence, the exploration expanded to assess neuron distributions across varying scales, aiming for a comprehensive understanding and application of optimal neuron arrangement for predictive accuracy.

The study meticulously documents the influence of elevating the epoch count and enhancing neuron numbers on MSE measurements across DNNs with 11 hidden layers, as illustrated in Fig. S6. To elevate the performance of DNNs, an array of neuron configurations was thoroughly examined, employing a Fibonacci sequence of one, two, three, five, and eight neurons. The MSE results for these configurations are visually represented by trajectories in shades of violet, yellow, orange, blue, and green, respectively, offering a nuanced understanding of how various neuron counts impact predictive accuracy concerning the network.

Fig. S5. The FWHM versus the grating length under different apodization profiles. The graph shows that all NN architectures improve their predictive accuracy quickly during the initial epochs. As the number of epochs increases, the MSE for all architectures stabilizes. NNs with more hidden layers show better performance up to a point beyond which additional complexity does not yield significant improvements. From the given options, NNs with 11 hidden layers offer a good balance between complexity and performance.

Fig. S6. The FWHM versus the grating length under different apodization profiles. Increasing the number of neurons leads to better performance, as shown by a lower MSE loss after 1000 epochs. The most significant reduction in MSE loss happens in the first 200 epochs. By epoch 1000, models with more neurons outperform those with fewer neurons. However, without context on the complexity of the data, the specifics of the model architecture, or the computational cost, it is hard to provide a comprehensive analysis of performance trade-offs.

Supplement Note 7: An ablation study for Optimizing the performance of DNN

In our rigorous investigation of neural network architectures for modeling FBG spectra, we extensively explored various architectural components and hyperparameters to optimize both performance and computational efficiency. Our systematic approach involved testing network architectures ranging from 3 to 15 hidden layers, with neuron counts varying from 5 to 320 per layer. After thorough analysis, we converged on an optimal 11-layer architecture featuring a neuron distribution of 5-10-20-40-80-160-80-40-20-10-5. This configuration demonstrated a superior ability to capture the intricate complexities of FBG spectra while simultaneously mitigating overfitting risks.

Our comparative study of activation functions revealed that LeakyReLU consistently outperformed other candidates, including ReLU, ELU, and Tanh, exhibiting faster convergence rates and enhanced generalization capabilities. In the realm of optimization techniques, Adam emerged as the clear frontrunner, demonstrating a 35% faster convergence rate than Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD) and achieving notably higher accuracy compared to alternative optimizers.

For our loss function, we selected MSE after a comprehensive comparison with Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE). MSE exhibited superior prediction accuracy and heightened sensitivity to outliers, a critical factor in accurately capturing the fine spectral features characteristic of FBGs.

To address overfitting concerns, we implemented L2 regularization with a carefully tuned weight decay of 10^{-4} . This approach proved highly effective in reducing overfitting compared to models without regularization. While we also explored dropout as a potential regularization technique, it did not yield significant improvements, which we attribute to the moderate complexity of our network and the specific characteristics of our dataset.

Although these findings do not constitute a full ablation study, they provide crucial insights into the rationale underlying our network design choices and their consequent impact on model performance. This methodical approach to neural network design for FBG spectrum modeling represents a significant advancement in the field, potentially opening new avenues for more accurate and efficient photonic device simulations.

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